

PHP DAN JAVASCRIPT GA QO`LLASH USULI

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PHP dan JavaScript ga qo'llash usuli

PHP dan JavaScript mustaqil ravishda ishlata oladi. Agarda, savol bo'lsa shu yerda hal qilishga o'runaman.

Xo'sh, brauser mavjud. Ushbu dastur html-fayllarini ekranga chiroyli ko'rsatadi. Ushbu fayl, brauserni faqatgina 2-ta joydan olish mumkin: ular Internet va kompyuter tarmog'i orqali. Ushbu brauser fayllarni kompyuter mahalliy tarmog'idan olsa, shu faylni kim bo'lsa ham o'zgartirishi mumkin. Misol uchun: dasturni Borland C++ yoki Delphida yaratish mumkin va u html da faylni 1000 barobar "salom" so'zini yozishi mumkin. Shundan so'ng, brauser uni foydalanuvchi ekraniga yuboradi. Faylni brauserga qayerdan kelganiga e'tibor bering. Unga buni aloqasi yo'q ammo, html faylini oxirida qabul qiladi.

Agar, fayl Internetdan paydo bo'lsa, brauser esa fayl haqida hech narsani bilmaydi: sanasini ham, o'lchamini ham (to'lliq sifati), haqiqiy ismini ham bilmaydi. Agar, fayl serverdagi qandaydir dastur ishining natijasi bo'lsa, demak, ushbu fayl ham brauser holatidagi o'tadi. Agar veb-katalogni php fayliga o'girsak, brauser uni o'zini qabul qilmaydi, faqatgina php ishining php-fayli natijalarini ko'rsatadi.

JavaScript nima narsa(JS)? U html demakdir. Boshqacha qilib aytganda, u bir nechta qo'shimcha teglar va boshqa hech nima emas. Agar, qandaydir php da ishlovchi dastur echo "**login kiriting**" ni echo "";, ga o'zgartirsa, bajarilayotgan operatsiya php dasturida aytiladi. Boshlanishida bizning faylda echo saqlanadi. Foydalanuvchiga muloqot davrida sahifada php bajariladi va u brauserga ishni natijalarini yuboradi. Shundan so'ng brauserda html kodi qoladi. Brauserga farqi yo'q, unga kod qayerdan kelganiga qiziqmaydi. Brauser html faylini oladi va uni ekranda aks ettiradi, JS kodini to'lliqligicha ko'rsatadi. PHP dan JS ga o'girish uchun nima qilish kerak? Eng avvalom bor shuni esdan chiqarmangki, php ni yuklash kerak va u html sahifasini yaratadi (bir vaqtda JS kodini yaratish mumkin).

Tasavvur qilingki, bizda shunaqa fayl bo'lgan deb:

```
<html>
<body>
2 + 3 =
< script>
a=2+3;
xujjat.write(a);
< /script>
</body>
</html>
```

PHP: yordamida o'zgartiradi.

```
<html>
```

```
<body>
2 + 3 =
< script>
a=<? echo 2+3; ?>;
xujjat .write(a);
< /script>
</body></html>
```

Va endi berilgan formulani PHP o'qiydi, keyin esa, html sahifasiga natijalarni joylashtiradi. Aks holda, JS dasturi ma'lumotini qabul qiladi, u oddiygina qo'shimcha effektini Php dasturda bajaradi va 2 va 3 qiymatni o'qiydi.

JavaScript da onlayn kalkulyator

Bu kalkulyator onlayn rejimida ishlaydigan boshqa kalkulyatordan farq qiladigan biz foydalanadigan kalkulyator strukturasi ishlaydigan sodda kalkulyator. Index.html quyidagi kurinishda

```
<HTML>
<HEAD>
<TITLE>JavaScript da onlayn kalkulyator </TITLE>
</HEAD>
<BODY BGCOLOR=#ffffff vlink=#0000ff>
<BR>
<center>
<BR>
<BASEFONT SIZE=3>
<table BORDER=0 WIDTH=486 CELLPADDING=3 CELLSPACING=0>
<tr><td><font FACE="helvetica,arial,geneva">
<br>
<br>
<TABLE>
<B>
<TABLE border=2 width=50 height=60 cellpadding=1 cellspacing=5>
<TR>
<TD colspan=3 align=middle>
<input name="ReadOut" type="Text" size=24 value="0" width=100%>
</TD>
<TD>
</TD>
<TD>
<input name="btnClear" type="Button" value=" C " onclick="Clear()">
</TD>
<TD><input name="btnClearEntry" type="Button" value=" CE " onclick="ClearEntry()">
</TD>
</TR>
<TR>
<TD>
```

```

<input name="btnSeven" type="Button" value=" 7 " onclick="NumPressed(7)">
</TD>
<TD>
<input name="btnEight" type="Button" value=" 8 " onclick="NumPressed(8)">
</TD>
<TD>
<input name="btnNine" type="Button" value=" 9 " onclick="NumPressed(9)">
</TD>
<TD>
</TD>
</TD>
<input name="btnNeg" type="Button" value=" +/- " onclick="Neg()">
</TD>
<TD>
<input name="btnPercent" type="Button" value=" % " onclick="Percent()">
</TD>
</TR>
<TR>
<TD>
<input name="btnFour" type="Button" value=" 4 " onclick="NumPressed(4)">
</TD>
<TD>
<input name="btnFive" type="Button" value=" 5 " onclick="NumPressed(5)">
</TD>
<TD>
<input name="btnSix" type="Button" value=" 6 " onclick="NumPressed(6)">
</TD>
</TD>
<TD align="middle"><input name="btnPlus" type="Button" value=" + "
onclick="Operation('+')">
</TD>
<TD align="middle"><input name="btnMinus" type="Button" value=" - " onclick="Operation('-
)'">
</TD>
</TR>
<TR>
<TD>
<input name="btnOne" type="Button" value=" 1 " onclick="NumPressed(1)">
</TD>
<TD>
<input name="btnTwo" type="Button" value=" 2 " onclick="NumPressed(2)">
</TD>
<TD>

```

```

<input name="btnThree" type="Button" value=" 3 " onclick="NumPressed(3)">
</TD>
<TD>
</TD>
<TD align="middle"><input name="btnMultiply" type="Button" value=" * "
onclick="Operation('*')">
</TD>
<TD align="middle"><input name="btnDivide" type="Button" value=" / "
onclick="Operation('/')">
</TD>
</TR>
<TR>
<TD>
<input name="btnZero" type="Button" value=" 0 " onclick="NumPressed(0)">
</TD>
<TD>
<input name="btnDecimal" type="Button" value=" ." onclick="Decimal()">
</TD>
<TD colspan="3">
</TD>
<TD>
<input name="btnEquals" type="Button" value=" =" onclick="Operation('=')">
</TD>
</TR>
</TABLE>
</TABLE>
</B>
</FORM>
</CENTER>
<font face="Verdana, Arial, Helvetica" size=2>
<SCRIPT LANGUAGE="JavaScript">
<!--
var FKeyPad = document.Keypad;
var Accum = 0;
var FlagNewNum = false;

var PendingOp = "";
function NumPressed (Num) {
if (FlagNewNum) {
FKeyPad.ReadOut.value = Num;
FlagNewNum = false;
}
else {
if (FKeyPad.ReadOut.value == "0")

```

```

FKeyPad.ReadOut.value = Num;
else
FKeyPad.ReadOut.value += Num;
}
}
function Operation (Op) {
var Readout = FKeyPad.ReadOut.value;
if (FlagNewNum && PendingOp != "");
else
{
FlagNewNum = true;
if ( '+' == PendingOp )

Accum += parseFloat(Readout);
else if ( '-' == PendingOp )
Accum -= parseFloat(Readout);
else if ( '/' == PendingOp )
Accum /= parseFloat(Readout);
else if ( '*' == PendingOp )
Accum *= parseFloat(Readout);
else
Accum = parseFloat(Readout);
FKeyPad.ReadOut.value = Accum;
PendingOp = Op;
}
}
function Decimal () {
var curReadOut = FKeyPad.ReadOut.value;
if (FlagNewNum) {
curReadOut = "0.";
FlagNewNum = false;
}
else
{
if (curReadOut.indexOf(".") == -1)
curReadOut += ".";
}
FKeyPad.ReadOut.value = curReadOut;
}
function ClearEntry () {
FKeyPad.ReadOut.value = "0";
FlagNewNum = true;
}
function Clear () {

```

```

Accum = 0;
PendingOp = "";
ClearEntry();
}
function Neg () {
FKeyPad.ReadOut.value = parseFloat(FKeyPad.ReadOut.value) * -1;
}
function Percent () {
FKeyPad.ReadOut.value = (parseFloat(FKeyPad.ReadOut.value) / 100) *
parseFloat(Accum);
}
// End -->
</SCRIPT>
</form>
</FONT>
</center>
</body>
</html>

```

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